

SHORT NOTES

Biogenesis of 3,4 - Coupling of Isoprenoids

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3-Methyl-3-butenyl 1-pyrophosphate (isopentenyl pyrophosphate) was identified as an intermediate in the enzymic conversion of mevalonic acid 5-phosphate to squalene¹. Enzymic isomerisation of the above pyrophosphate to $\beta\beta$ -dimethylallyl pyrophosphate has been reported by Lynen *et al.*², who also has identified geranyl pyrophosphate and farnesyl pyrophosphate as intermediates in the biogenesis of squalene from mevalonic acid by cell-free yeast extracts. A mechanism has been suggested³⁻⁵ for the biosynthesis of geranyl pyrophosphate from isopentenyl pyrophosphate on the basis of the postulation of alkylation of the isopentenyl pyrophosphate by an allylic carbonium ion derived from $\beta\beta$ -dimethylallyl pyrophosphate, polarisation of the double bond in isopentenyl pyrophosphate molecule being effected by the electro-negative inductive effect of the methyl group with the concurrent anchimeric assistance⁵ of the pyrophosphate moiety. This mechanism neatly explained the head-to-tail (1,4) union of the isoprenoid moieties in geraniol and farnesol. We report herein an extension of this mechanism to explain as well the 3,4-coupling of isoprenoid moieties in natural terpenoids.

1. Bloch *et al.*, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1958, **44**, 998; *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1959, **234**, 2595.
2. *Angew. Chem.*, 1958, **70**, 738; 1959, **71**, 657.
3. Bloch *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1959, **234**, 1424.
4. Cornforth, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1959, No. 19, 29.

Instead of the reaction between one molecule of isopentenyl pyrophosphate and one molecule of $\beta\beta$ -dimethylallyl pyrophosphate, an alkylation reaction is envisaged between two molecule of $\beta\beta$ -dimethylallyl pyrophosphate (I & II), one (I) supplying the carbonium ion (electrophile) and the other (II) acting as a nucleophile, which is formed by polarisation of the carbon—carbon double bond due to the electro-negative inductive effect of the two methyl groups with the concurrent anchimeric assistance of the pyrophosphate moiety. The intermediate (III) then collapses to the stable product, lavandulyl pyrophosphate (IV). This offers a rational explanation of the formation of natural compounds like lavandulol (V), the structure of which is derived from a 3,4-coupling of two isoprene units⁶.

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Received February 2, 1964.

5. Cf. Johnson *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, No. 12, 21.

6. Simonsen and Owan, "The Terpenes", Cambridge University Press, 1947, p. 54.